

Bordering Brussels

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

citizen science, Brussels, history, borders

Purpose of this paper

BORDERING BRUSSELS is an innovative response to the need to provide non-elite knowledge on bordering practices within and beyond Brussels in past and present. Working with a mix of disciplines – (A) history, (B) border studies, (C) political sciences, (D) citizen science and in a dialogue with (E) art and technology – and using our open science methods, the project aims to advance our knowledge about, and unravel, where people in Brussels place(d) borders and why that mattered/s to them. The project has several aims:

A. It is time to write the **history** of the birth and growth of the Brussels-Capital Region no longer primarily from the perspective of institutions, as ‘changes in perceptions of the other are generally a bottom-up rather than a top-down process and are brought about by increased interaction and movement of borderlanders’ (Newman, 17).

B. It is time to write Brussels into the global field of **border studies**. The field’s multimodal ways of interpretation can help us to move beyond the – still dominant in the public sphere – binary interpretations of a border as a line dividing territory (Amilhat-Szary & Giraut (eds.); Müller; Rajaram & Grundy-Warr (eds.); Weier a.o.).

C. After **deliberative democracy** (‘the capability of transforming citizens’ opinions and attitudes by means of deliberation’) was introduced in Brussels by means of inter-group settings (Caluwaerts & Reuchamps), this project uses crowdsourcing experiments with a deliberative

technique with the aim to generate new research questions on experiences and perceptions that matter to people.

D. We are moving towards a peer-to-peer society. **Citizen science** is booming in the natural sciences but remains underrepresented in the humanities (Wildschut; Oswald & Smolarski (eds.)). **BORDERING BRUSSELS** serves to offer new knowledge and develop a new method in order to enhance opportunities for citizens to co-create future science agendas (Macnaghten).

E. The urgency of finding hybrid innovative solutions on the nexus of **Science–Technology–Art** has been recognized: ‘Today we no longer have the right to pretend that we command a unique position from which we can view the truth about the world. We must learn not to judge different areas of knowledge, culture, or art, but to combine them and to establish new ways of coexistence with those who enable us to meet the unique demands of our time.’ (Ilya Prigogine & Isabelle Stengers). **BORDERING BRUSSELS** facilitates the search for synergies beyond disciplines and sectors in exchange with citizens and artists.

Design/methodology/approach

The starting point of **BORDERING BRUSSELS** is the online open database of oral sources of *Bruxelles nous appartient / Brussel behoort ons toe*, an organization gathering, developing and supporting participatory sound art with city dwellers in order to display the diverse identities of the city, containing 2,856 entries about Brussels (both full interviews and interview fragments) (Janssen). These will be approached in three ways:

- an interdisciplinary literature study and a narrative analysis of these sources will be conducted in order to situate the collection within the historical context of bordering processes in Brussels. A TED talk will be recorded situating the scientific value of the collection in Dutch, French and English.

- a selection will be made of the most popular fragments giving information about practices related to bordering Brussels starting from 1970. These are transcribed, made available in three languages and posted on an online platform.

- an Artist is invited to offer an acoustic artistic input inspired by the fragments and, together with the Researcher, build the **BORDERING BRUSSELS BOX (BBB)** synergizing the TED talk, the online platform (touch screen and reference to App) and the artistic input.

BBB will meet citizens during its journey at festivals and in various public spaces. BBB invites citizens to the platform, where a joint inquiry is organized through crowdsourcing in three steps: crowd community sense-making, co-creation of clusters through crowd validation and the generation of new research questions.

Findings/expected Findings

The last step of the research project will take place during an MA course taught by the Researcher with student-citizens, as well as during a workshop with researchers of the Centre for Information, Documentation and Research on Brussels (scholars). With the help of a software programme, citizens and scholars are asked to include the clusters into an open knowledge path, thereby enabling them to be situated within existing knowledge and gaps to be detected, which potentially include new research questions.

What is original/value of paper

This project gives voice to city dwellers in order to come to a multifaceted understanding of the meaning(s) of bordering processes within Brussels and beyond. It guides the data gathered by citizens by means of peer-to-peer research with citizens to new research questions about how city dwellers create(d) borders for themselves and others.

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